

Synthesis of New Chloro-Anthraquinones¹

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Manuscript received 3 July 1975; accepted 22 April 1976

The synthesis of two new chloro-anthraquinones, 5,6,7,8-tetra-chloro-1-hydroxy-4-methyl and 4,5,6,7,8-penta-chloro-1-hydroxy anthraquinones by Friedel and Crafts reaction in presence of $AlCl_3$ and $NaCl$ melt is described.

ANTHRAQUINONES having more than one chlorine atoms have earlier been prepared^{2,3} but not reported to have any toxic property while two new anthraquinones 5,6,7,8-tetrachloro-1-hydroxy-4-methyl (IVa) anthraquinone and 4,5,6,7,8-penta-chloro-1-hydroxy (IVb) anthraquinone, prepared by Friedel and Crafts acylation and cyclisation reactions are responding for such behaviour⁴.

The compounds IVa and IVb were prepared by condensing tetra-chloro-phthalic anhydride (I) with *p*-cresol (IIa) and 4-chlorophenol (IIb) separately in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3 \cdot NaCl$ melt.

The compounds IIIa and IIIb were characterised on the basis of analytical and spectral studies as 2-(2'-hydroxy-5'-methyl-benzoyl) 3,4,5,6-tetra-chloro benzoic acid and 2-(2'-hydroxy-5' chloro-benzoyl)-3,4,5,6-tetra-chloro benzoic acids respectively. The structures of IVa and IVb were also characterised on the basis of analytical and spectral results.

The compounds IIIa and IIIb on cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid gave IVa and IVb respectively increasing their yields to approximately 95% and also confirming their structures.

The crude reaction mixtures were purified with the and column chromatography using silica gel as absorbent and benzene, benzene-methanol mixture as eluents. The IIa condensate gave IIIa and IVa while IIb gave IIIb and IVb.

The reaction conditions and properties of reaction products are summarised in Table 1.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. R. C. Kapoor of this University for providing necessary facilities and to Prof. Paul J. Scheuer, University of Hawaii for spectral determination.

TABLE I - PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF CHLORO ANTHRAQUINONES IVA AND IVB

Friedel and Crafts acylation and cyclisation with tetra-chloro phthalic anhydride in AlCl₃ NaCl melt

S.No.	Phenol	Reaction temp °C	time Min.	Products isolated and appearance	IR (ν_{max}) absorption at	M. P. C	Yields %	Elemental analysis
1.	IIa	200 -225	40	IIIa light yellow needles	3000, 2800, 1720, 1625, 1600, 1318, 1220, 825, 790 and 760 cm ⁻¹	234	22	C, 45.33 H, 2.12 Cl, 35.8
				IVa yellow needles	1660, 1640, 1565, 1450, 1360, 1209, 840, 820-I & 730 cm ⁻¹	247°	76	C, 48.26 H, 1.45 Cl, 37.8
2.	IIb	200-220	45	IIIb light yellow green	3410, 3110, 2890, 1720, 1640, 1570, 1220, 1200, 1170, 870, 820 and 720 cm ⁻¹	215°	20	C, 40.26 H, 1.43 Cl, 42.5
				IVb dark yellow	1690, 1640, 1570, 1520, 1375, 1295, 1225, 1145, 1075, 820, and 805 cm ⁻¹	252°	75	C, 42.15 H, 1.12 Cl, 45.0

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- These studies are in progress.